

STUDENTS IN THE ART OF EMBROIDERY IN UZBEKISTAN INTRODUCTION TO SCHOOLS

Choriyev Nurislam Nuritdinovich

Teacher of Termiz State University

E-mail:nurislomchoriyev69@gmail.com

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Summary. This article emphasizes the educational and educational value of teaching students in embroidery schools in Uzbekistan.

Key words and concepts: embroidery, school of embroidery, principle, process, principle, method, color, color, regularity, weights.

It is important to introduce students to embroidery art schools. During the time of the Khans, masters of folk art began to gather in cities such as Khiva, Kokan, Bukhara, and Samarkand. Painters from Ferghana and Bukhara often came to Samarkand, and masters from Kokan and Margilan came to Tashkent to decorate buildings. This plays a major role in the further development of embroidery schools, the creation of unique compositions, and the enrichment of the color complex. Although these embroideries are similar to each other, each school of embroidery is distinguished by its own laws, principles, work method, and color scheme.

Tashkent embroidery school. Tashkent embroideries are distinguished by their elegance and the gradual transition of colors to each other, strict adherence to a specific color scheme, and the frequent use of geometric and plant-like embroideries. Embroideries are often worked in green gamma. In Islamic embroidery, complex girikh embroidery with clearly stylized moonflower, cotton, cotton, three leaves, shukufta, leafy flower and other elements is also widely used.

Khiva embroidery school. Khiva embroidery is fundamentally different from Samarkand, Tashkent, Fergana, Bukhara. In Khiva embroidery, mainly blue and green colors were used a lot. The composition of Islamic embroidery consists of a branch, a rose, a rose, a leaf, a pea, a flower, and a simple moon. Many star-forming gyrikhs are used, and the center is enriched with spiral Islamic embroidery. Khiva embroidery is generally made on the basis of mixed compositions.

Bukhara and Samarkand embroidery schools. Bukhara embroidery is distinguished by the complexity and attractiveness of its compositions. Bukhara embroideries are distinguished by the use of complex gyrikhs in precise and precise sizes, and the special attention paid to the rhythm of leaves, fruits, and flowers in vegetable embroideries. Samarkand embroidery is similar to Tashkent and Ferghana methods. Samarkand embroideries are distinguished by their extreme floweriness, the mobility and liveliness of their leaves and flowers. The embroideries are first blue and then green. In order to further strengthen the above information in the minds of students, it is important to complete the following educational task (Table 1).

The rule for working using the insert method 1. Read the text of the lecture and put the following marks in the margin of the text: V - I know; + new information for me; - denies information that I know; ? - unclear (requiring clarification) additional information. 2. Formalize the obtained results in the form of a table.

Topic questions	B	-	+	?
1. Types of folk art				
2. Embroidery art schools				
3. The role of embroidery in practical art				
4. History of embroidery art				

Questions to revise:

- **List the types of Uzbek folk art. What is a pattern?**
- **What kind of science is applied art and what is its essence?**
- **Who do you know from the master embroiderers?**

In the educational process, students should be treated as individuals, various pedagogical technologies and modern methods should be used, they should be encouraged to think independently, freely, to research, to approach each issue creatively, to feel responsible, to carry out scientific research work, to analyze, to make effective use of scientific literature, the most important thing. , will increase their interest in study, science and their chosen profession.

Achieving such a result requires the use of information technologies in the educational process. The technologies are very different. We will dwell on the organization of some of them and the procedure for their transfer.

The "Blitz-survey" method helps students to correctly organize the sequence of actions, to think logically, to choose the necessary from various opinions and information based on the subject they are studying, as well as to respect the opinion of others and to be able to convey their own opinion to them, as well as their own activities, aimed at learning to plan the day. through this method, students will be able to determine the sequence of actions shown on the papers distributed to them individually, to be able to convey their opinion to others in small groups or to stay in their opinion, and to be able to agree with others.

"Charkhapalak" technology helps to teach students to remember the topics covered, to think logically, to independently answer correctly to the given questions and to self-evaluate, and in a short time the teacher evaluates the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications of all students. This technology can be organized in the form of individual, small group and team training.

"Zinama-zina" technology gives effective results in teaching students to think and remember individually and in small groups on the topics defined in the program, to memorize the acquired knowledge, to summarize the collected thoughts and to express them in writing, pictures, and drawings. This technology is conducted in writing and presented with students individually or in groups.

Providing education to students in accordance with the requirements of the times, using various pedagogical technologies and modern methods, encourages them to think independently and freely, to search, to approach each issue creatively.

Information technology is rapidly entering every field. We can see confirmation of this in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On further development of

computerization and introduction of information and communication technologies".

In fact, it is difficult to find subjects in education today that do not use computer capabilities. Various programs of information technologies applied to all subjects in the educational process have been developed and are widely used in practice.

In particular, the Corel Draw graphic program facilitates the creation and coloring of embroidery compositions in the art of embroidery. This program offers a lot of possibilities for developing graphic design pages, analyzing photos and vector animation. Also, the program reduces several times the actions needed to create a composition and perform it. For example, new elements: ellipses, right angles and curves will be given the required size and rotation angle by double-clicking the mouse button.

The Corel Draw professional graphic program has great capabilities in creating and coloring embroidery compositions, and through this program, you can color the embroidery composition in different colors and choose the appropriate color in a short time. We will consider this process by creating and coloring a girix embroidery composition.

To start the Corel Draw program, find its icon on the desktop, hover over it, and double-click the left mouse button. If this picture is not found on the screen, bring the mouse pointer over the "Pusk" menu in the taskbar below and click the left button once. The "programmy" section is selected from the list that appears. From the list on the right, find the line Corel Draw and click on it once with the left mouse button. After completing these steps, the Corel Draw program will start. From the "Nabor instrumentov" (tools) menu, select the "rectangular" command and use the "ctrl" key to draw a square shape.

Then the command "svobodnaya forma" is selected from the "Nabor instrumentov" menu, vertical and horizontal lines are drawn using the "ctrl" key. Then select the "ellipse" command and use the "ctrl" key to draw a circle with the lower right point of the square as the center. The radius of a circle is equal to the side of a square. Using the command "arc" (arc) of the menu, one of the dimensions is equal to 900 and one to 1800, an arc is created, and a horizontal line is drawn from the created point. The left side of the square is connected with this line and point b is formed. Then, using the command "ellipse" command "ctrl" button menu "arc" to create an arc centered on the point V of the square. A vertical line is drawn from the resulting point s and the point d is formed. Then, using the "ellipse" command, the "ctrl" button, and the "arc" command of the menu, an arc is drawn with the point A of the square as the center. A horizontal line is drawn from the resulting point e, and point j is found. Then, using the "ellipse" command, the "ctrl" button, the "arc" command of the menu, an arc is drawn with the point D of the square as the center. We draw a vertical line from the resulting z point and form the i point. An arc is drawn from point I formed by the intersection of horizontal and vertical lines with point D as the center, as shown above. The intersection of the arc and the square forms the points r and r.

An arc is drawn from point R to point j as the center, points s and t are formed in the above order, a straight line is drawn from point r to point p, and from it to point t formed by the intersection of a vertical line with a semicircle, and a point is formed. Parallel to this line, a line is drawn from point r and point f is formed, and points u and f are connected, resulting in a rectangle. The same rectangle is also formed in the opposite diagonal direction. In the next step, lines are drawn from point j to points o and n, from point E to points m and l, from point Z to points o and l, and from point I to points m and n. Now we connect the necessary points

and form a geometric shape on all sides of the square. Finally, from the sum of these geometric shapes, the girix embroidery composition that we expect is formed (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Girix embroidery composition created using Corel Draw graphic software.

Such training will increase their interest in education, science and their chosen profession in organizing scientific and creative work and conducting research in the future. Most of us know that today information technologies and their concepts are considered somewhat popular and they have entered into practice. It can be said that they are based on a non-traditional teaching system.

- Using non-traditional methods during classes, using its possibilities is a responsible task for every teacher. In the implementation of these tasks, it is necessary to pay serious attention to the following aspects: first of all, improving the logical thinking and professional skills of teachers in order to organize the educational process of embroidery art in the spirit of creativity and curiosity; application of information technologies in teaching the art of embroidery to teachers, finding effective methods and methods of spiritual-ethical and educational education and using them effectively;

through the ability of the teacher to act as a modern creator in the art of embroidery, to educate students' positive, economic initiative, ability and talent, to raise their national pride, spiritual, moral and aesthetic outlook; to increase the sincerity of demands regarding the restoration, preservation, strengthening and development of the spiritual, moral and cultural achievements of our nation in the way of building a humane civil society. The successful solution of such issues is related to the high level of knowledge and literacy of students in this field, as well as the effective completion of their activities aimed at acquiring their chosen professions.

It is important to implement folk craft classes in higher educational institutions on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies, to provide modern teaching-methodical complexes and didactic aspects of the educational process in the formation of the new content of applied art education, and to correctly solve the scientific and practical issues of training in this field. Also, students of higher educational institutions should understand the essence of problematic issues from applied and artistic decorative arts, in order to find a solution to certain tasks, it should be carried out in connection with their personal needs, interest, ability, talent, and potential. it allows to educate thinking, spiritual, enlightened people.

It is worth noting that today in our country great attention is paid to the education of young people and their development into mature specialists in the future. In this regard, the large-scale implementation of information technologies in the educational process requires solving the problems of complex design of education by enriching the content of education, improving it, accelerating the acquisition of students' knowledge, conducting group and individual exercises.

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